

THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article describes some problems and their solutions related to the importance of information and communication technologies in the development of students' creative competencies.*

Keywords: *student, teacher, creativity, competence, information and communication technology, creative activity.*

According to the strategy of action on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Priority directions of the development of the social sphere", educational institutions are equipped with modern educational tools and laboratory equipment, computer equipment and teaching-methodical manuals. To improve their material and technical base by carrying out effective work on equipment, to fundamentally increase the quality of education, to increase the effectiveness of teaching while educational institutions are fully equipped with information technology tools - it is noted that application in the educational process is one of the requirements of the present day [1].

Today's task of education is to teach students to be able to work independently in the conditions of an informational educational environment that is increasing day by day, to effectively use modern information technologies in various fields and to use the information flow wisely. It is necessary to create the opportunity and conditions for continuous independent work and to teach creative thinking and independent decision-making. The solution to this problem naturally depends on the quality of training of the main organizer of this process - teachers [5; B. 12].

Many studies have been conducted to study the characteristics of effective interaction between students and computers. However, the specific features of teaching and developing creative competencies of students in the environment of information technologies have not been specially studied. Therefore, the introduction of special use of computer technologies and software capabilities in this regard is timely. Ignoring or rejecting these features leads to a drastic reduction in the effectiveness of existing computer programs. The analysis of existing studies shows that the process of teaching creative thinking students is characterized by its own characteristics. Usually creative thinking students need attention and support no less than their peers and classmates. Such students demonstrate a high degree of independence in the process of understanding the educational material. Students emphasize the ability of students to learn new educational material independently as a unique factor indicating the presence of abilities. The principle of individualization of education, which is important for the realization of abilities, the development of special computer programs that expand the student's independent education and the possibilities of its development, as well as computerization of theoretical knowledge control, psychological support of students and pedagogical training fits. In traditional educational programs aimed at acquiring theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies, the development of creative

abilities is considered as a secondary issue. Our research shows that such an approach cannot be used to teach students who think creatively, because it has a negative effect on the psychological development of students.

At the same time, the British philosopher and mathematician Alfred North Whitehead, who lived and worked in the 19th century, said that "society will not achieve democratic success until the educational system does not well shape people's philosophical outlook" [2; B. 496] confirms that even today the intensity of information flow in the world requires the transition of the positive attitude of man to the environment and social being to a new qualitative stage.

Innovative educational technologies and integrative use of information technologies:

ensures the continuity of "science - education - practice";

there will be enough reasons to provide detailed information on the purpose, content, important pedagogical features of innovative educational technology, their methodological and informational didactic support and capabilities;

the use of new ways of using information technologies based on an innovative approach to the use of traditional educational methods is the basis for achieving educational effectiveness;

in the use of innovative educational technology, it is possible to make consequential changes through information technologies, to study, master and use similar scientific and theoretical sources.

It is very important to take an individual approach to involving students in the environment of electronic information resources, that is, to take into account the personal and psychological capabilities of students, to support the student's interactive work procedure in the network of electronic information resources. Interactivity is the ability of the user to actively interact with the source of scientific and methodological information, to choose it at will, to change the speed of effective transmission [4; B. 60].

Educational opportunities that indicate the readiness of students to actively work with electronic information resources can be determined through the following directions:

- software computer tools, information resources in the global network and computer use;
- effective use of the search system and directories;
- finding necessary information according to the purpose of education;
- to explain new information, form and justify alternative views, understand who needs new information;
- storing information and using it in everyday life;
- processing and presentation of information for the educational process [6; B. 79].

If the student knows all of the above, then he can easily work in the electronic information resource network. If students know how to effectively communicate with each other, then they can effectively use the possibilities of electronic information resources. Only after acquiring the necessary intellectual theoretical knowledge and practical skills, students can move to the stage of effective use of the electronic information resource network.

It is known that in traditional training, the search for new material was carried out by using additional literature on science. The teacher would recommend the necessary books, and the student would submit a summary of the necessary passage. In this case, a formal approach that does not require active mental work may prevail. Currently, these problems are solved with the help of electronic information resource. At the same time, as mentioned above, a number of new

problems arose, such as how to get the necessary information from a large number of materials, how to extract the main necessary idea, and determine the accuracy of the obtained information. The solution of the mentioned problems mainly depends on the special tasks of different content, which are created on a new topic. Assignments should be scientifically relevant in content, appropriate to students' level of theoretical knowledge and interest, updated, stimulating independent knowledge and easy completion of assignments [3; B. 92].

Technical changes in the field of Internet social services are so numerous and intense that the development of the methodology of using Web technologies in education is considered one of the most urgent complex problems of today.

According to the analysis of methodical publications and foreign experiences of recent years, Web-technologies, due to their didactic features such as simplicity, speed, effectiveness in organizing the information environment, multimedia, interactivity, reliability and security, organize the educational process, organize pedagogical practice provides an opportunity to find a relatively more complete solution to the problem of optimization of its management.

Based on web technologies, the design and development of pedagogical activity is not only creative, but also has a comprehensive content. Therefore, didactic "What should be taught?" and "How to teach?" a new quality of socially asked questions is formed [6; B. 25].

If we consider Web-technology as an educational technology, the following main didactic factors can be cited:

- Educational interactivity, motivation and creativity;
- sociality and openness of information;
- multi-functionality and interoperability.

We determined the urgency of the problem of developing students' creative competencies based on web technologies with the following factors:

Motivational factor. In the effective application of web technologies to the educational process:

- maximum consideration of individual educational opportunities, interests and needs of students; there is an opportunity to choose a fast pace and different levels of training sessions; formation of creative intellectual abilities of students [6; B. 7-8].

Structural factor. Among the educational possibilities of web technologies:

- creation of digital electronic educational resources, such as interactive tables, pictures, posters and developments related to sections and specific topics of the educational subject; creating tests of different complexity on the computer.

These led to the establishment of new forms of improvement of the system of training future specialists based on Web-technologies - educational network cooperation, which is an integral part of the modern education system.

In short, the integrative characteristic of personal creativity of teachers dealing with creative thinking students depends on the development of their own personal creative activity. This position is that if the pedagogue is not ready for his creative development, does not feel the importance of implementing such processes, if he does not have the ability to implement it in relation to himself, then it is clear that he will not allow his students to have the potential of creative talent gifted by nature in advance. unable to start unlocking mechanisms.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «O‘zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo‘yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to‘g‘risida»gi PF-4947-son Farmoni. –Toshkent: Adolat, 2018.
2. Альфред Норт Уайтхед. Избранные работы по философии. –Москва: Прогресс, 1990. – С. 496.
3. Банина Т.С., Вавилова Л.Н. Современные способы активизации обучения. –М.: Академия, 2008. – 176 с.
4. Ibragimova G.N. Interfaol o‘qitish metodlari va texnologiyalari asosida talabalarning kreativlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish: ped.fan.bo‘y.fal.doktori (PhD) diss. –Toshkent, 2017. – 154 b.
5. Ниматулаев М.М. Подготовка учителей к использованию web-технологий для самостоятельного повышения квалификации. Автореферат дисс ... докт. пед. наук. – Москва: 2012. - 48 с.
6. Tursunov S.Q. Ta‘limda elektron axborot resurslarini yaratish va ularni joriy qilishning metodik asoslari (pedagogika oliy ta‘lim muassasalari «Web-dizayn» fani misolida). Ped.fan.nomz... diss. –Toshkent, 2011. -138 b.